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Conditional Cash Transfer Impact and Beneficiaries' Well-Being Status in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

Author's Details:

Bilkisu O. Abdulkarim¹, Samson Olayemi Sennuga¹, Joseph Bamidele³, Funso O. Alabuja², and Osho-Lagunju Bankole¹

¹Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, FCT, P.M.B. 117, Abuja Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Sociology, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja, FCT, P.M.B. 117, Abuja Nigeria

³Faculty of Business and Law, University of Northampton, Northampton, UK

Corresponding author's E-mail: dr.yemisennuga@yahoo.co.uk

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Abstract

The study determines the effect of conditional cash transfer on the wellbeing status of beneficiaries in Abaji Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria. Sample size of 100 beneficiaries was selected using multi-stage sampling procedure. Structured questionnaire complimented with interview scheduled were used for data collection Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (frequency, count, percentage and mean) and inferential (Wellbeing Status Index and Logit Regression Model). The result revealed 79% of the beneficiaries were female with mean age of 47.3 years. The mean household size and that of farming experience were 6 persons and 16.8 years respectively. The beneficiaries were satisfy with personal relationship ($\bar{X} = 5.64$), personal safety ($\bar{X} = 5.62$) and life achievement ($\bar{X} = 5.62$) wellbeing indicators. The coefficient of coefficient of educational level (0.3214183), distance to CCT center (0.2295646), cooperative membership (1.36954), access to sanitation (0.9016355) and enrolment of children in school (1.054859) had significant effect on the wellbeing status of the beneficiaries. The most problem associated with CCT were corruption among official ($\bar{X} = 2.50$), poor road network ($\bar{X} = 2.32$) and poor government policy ($\bar{X} = 2.10$). It is recommended that government should inject more funds to the programme in order to enhance beneficiaries' wellbeing status, intervention programme should be brought closer to beneficiaries dwelling place for easy accessibility.

Keywords: Effect, Conditional Cash Transfer, Well-being, beneficiarie

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common forms of social assistance in low and middle-income nations is conditional cash transfers (CCT). For instance, there are currently 26 conditional cash transfer programs running in Latin America and the Caribbean, benefiting approximately 135 million individuals (Jerving, 2020). Moreover, CCTs are growing quickly: more than fifty countries operate CCTs currently, which is more than twice as many as in 2010 (World Bank, 2014). Programs known as Conditional Cash Transfers (CCTs) have proliferated in

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emerging and undeveloped nations as a means of reducing current poverty and investing in human capital that might eventually improve living conditions for families (Sennuga et al., 2020). When governments provide money to poor families on a regular basis as a supplemental source of income, the first purpose is achieved. By conditioning the cash transfers on certain behaviors, such as visiting health facilities, immunizing kids, and enrolling kids in school, the second purpose is accomplished. However, these initiatives may also have a significant influence on recipient families' time management choices, particularly in relation to time spent working (Jerving, 2020).

Social services should reduce poverty without making beneficiaries dependent on them, according to policymakers, you name it. One option is to encourage families to invest in their family members' human capital with the money they receive from social programs so that they will have greater prospects once the transfers stop. It is common knowledge that incomes and education are closely associated. A long-term policy would therefore be similar to tying a cash transfer program to certain actions that represent an investment in human capital (Hoddinott et al. 2014).

However, Social Investment Programmes is a multifaceted concept with different dimensions that relate to a number of public policy areas (World Bank, 2016). Social Investment Programmes (SIP) plays a significant role in today's debates about the importance of social spending and the future of welfare states of low and middle income countries. The programme constitute a healthy public policy initiative as it has potential to address the social determinants of health and health inequalities, social capital, employment and social cohesion, nutrition and dietary diversity (Behman *et al.*, 2016). Since the establishment of the programmes in 2015, these programmes combined have supported more than four million beneficiaries country-wide through a fair and transparent process supported by the Ministry of Budget and National Planning (MBNP) and other notable Ministry Departments and Agencies MDAs with aligned goals (Ibrahim, 2017).

In an attempt to achieve the goal of reducing poverty among the poor and vulnerable households, the Conditional Cash Transfers (CCTs) was introduced (Department for International Development, 2015). Amongst other functions, CCTs functions as social assistance tools that are mainly designed to achieve short-term poverty reduction and long-term human capital development. Conditional Cash Transfer like other Social investment Programmes provide new ways to effectively allocate public and private capital to address social, economic and environmental challenges at the global, national, regional and local levels (United Nation Developmental Programme (UNDP), 2015). CCTs are programmes that transfer cash, generally to poor households, on the conditions that those households make pre-specified investments in the human capital of their children (Fiszbein *et al.*, 2014). These investments are usually health and education related and often requires periodic medical check-ups and school attendance for children. In order to alleviate current poverty and offer investments in human capital that enhance families' living situations over time, conditional cash transfer (CCT) schemes have proliferated in developing nations. When governments provide poor families money each month, the first objective is achieved. The second objective is accomplished by tying the financial transfers to particular actions, like kids attending school on a regular basis. Yet, these initiatives might also have an effect on how recipient households choose to spend their time, particularly in terms of how much time is spent working.

However, since the inception of the programmes in 2015 to date, independent study of the effects of Conditional Cash on the well-being of the beneficiaries Federal Capital Territory Abuja has been scanty, therefore this research is taking the challenge of filling this research vacuum of assessing National Social Investment Programmes and the well-being of beneficiaries in terms of their income, feeding, health, educational enrollment, and general well-being to empirically compare its achievement with the stated vision and mission of the programmes, the research will assess the effects of National Social Investment Programmes on the well-being of beneficiaries Federal Capital Territory Abuja and suggest recommendations of possible

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solutions to the factors militating the implementation of National Social Investment Programmes and sustainability of the programmes in the study area. The research tend to address these objectives, describe the socio-economic characteristic of CCT beneficiaries, determine the wellbeing status of CCT beneficiaries, determine the effect of CCT on beneficiaries wellbeing status and examine the constraints associated with CCT.

Impact of Conditional Cash Transfer on poverty reduction

A social policy known as conditional cash transfer (CCT) outlines requirements that must be satisfied before recipients can receive funds from the donor(s). The requirements include, among other things, attending important health services like prenatal, postnatal, child health, and nutrition, ensuring that kids attend school at least half the time, and participating in skill-training programs (Ahmed et al., 2010; Abayomi et al., 2021). The number of programs that provide financial grants to low-income households according to a set of conditions (such as attendance at school, visits to medical facilities, or participation in information sessions) has increased significantly during the past ten years. A large body of research has demonstrated that conditional cash transfer programs can, in the near term, reduce poverty and have a good influence on beneficiaries' health, nutrition, and attendance at school (Adedayo et al., 2020; Sennuga et al., 2020)

Impacts on subjective wellbeing

Although there is evidence that CCTs decrease poverty and promote the building of human capital, it is uncertain if they enhance users' subjective wellbeing. This issue is crucial because income and other financial indicators that economists have historically used to measure gains in quality of life have recently come under intense criticism. These monetary measurements are alluring because they can be measured relatively easily, but they miss out on important facets of the human experience like freedom, fairness, and general happiness. As a result, there is a growing consensus regarding the significance of using indicators like subjective wellbeing to gauge how well individuals are truly living their lives.

However, Hoddinott et al. (2014) examines how much the participants' subjective wellbeing improves as a result of Colombia's Families Accion Urbano (FAU) urban conditional cash transfer program. This study is the only one to date to examine this issue with a thorough causal research approach. Three years into the program, the authors discover that participation raises both total household income and contentment with income. Participation in the program leads to an increase in food expenditures, food satisfaction, formal employment, and job satisfaction. Participation in a program, however, does not seem to improve general life satisfaction. This second conclusion, in particular, is in line with the hypothesis that subjective assessments of wellbeing are likely domain-specific and that assessments of subjective well-being on the basis of one's overall quality of life are likely to be noisy indicators of wellbeing.

The role of conditionality

It is uncertain whether the conditions put on families or the monetary transfers used in CCT have an impact on educational outcomes and the accumulation of human capital. Theoretically, conditional transfers are less effective policy tools than, say, unconditional transfers in the absence of educational market failures, such as externalities. By contrasting the educational outcomes of girls who were randomly assigned to receive a conditional transfer with girls who were assigned to an unconditional transfer, Ahmed, et al., (2010) investigate this hypothesis. The authors discover that compared to females assigned to the unconditional transfer, those assigned to the CCT had greater rates of school attendance, reduced dropout rates, and superior achievement.

Similar conclusions are drawn based on data from Ecuador and a meta-analysis of conditional and unconditional cash transfers. Transfer policies that make enrollment outcomes expressly conditional, track compliance, and penalize non-compliance have a considerably greater impact (Alam, 2020). The evidence in support of placing restrictions on families points to market failures in the provision of education in

underdeveloped nations. An example of a specific sort of market failure that Staunton and Collins (2002) find evidence for is educational externalities. Friends of participating students also increased their attendance at school as a result of the CCT program investigated by Barrera-Osorio et al. (2008). However, the program also had unfavorable spillover effects on households, particularly on females. Compared to sisters of non-participants, participants' sisters are less likely to attend school and are more likely to be employed. Yet, conditionality and program targeting come with significant administrative costs. On the other hand, conditionality and targeting appear to increase educational achievements and the efficiency of CCTs' redistribution compared to no-conditions and universality. One question is whether it is possible to retain at least part of the human capital benefits of CCTs through less onerous program regulations given this interplay between the costs and benefits of conditionality and targeting.

Consequently, Alam (2020). demonstrate in the context of a pilot project in Morocco that providing a small cash transfer and loosely linking it to the goal of education - without an explicit conditionality—raises awareness of the value of education and boosts short-term school enrollment even in the absence of formal incentives. Contrarily, adding specific conditions has no positive impact on student enrolment. Our findings show that, due to smaller transfer amounts and lower administrative expenses, a tiny transfer linked to an educational "nudge" may be much more cost-effective than a conventional conditional cash transfer. Yet, it is unknown whether the "nudge's" educational effects would last over time.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in FCT, Nigeria. FCT is the capital city of Nigeria located in the centre of country it is a planned city and was built mainly in the 1980s replacing the country`s most populous city of Lagos as the capital on 12 December 1991. Abuja geography is defined by Aso Rock a 400metre (1,300ft) monolith left by water erosion. The FCT covers an area of 8000 square kilometers. The city`s population is hugely diverse, and groups that reside in Abuja include Gwari, Afo, Hausa, Koro, Bassa, Gade. The official language of the city is English. Although other languages are spoken, including Igbo, Fulani, and Yoruba. Approximately half of the city`s residents are Muslim, 40% are Christian, and the remainder follow other religions (Abuja Geographical Information System, 2018). As expected in a country with very high rural urban migration, Abuja has a population of 1,406,239 (National Population Commission, 2006) with annual growth rate of 6.11%, Abuja has a projected population of 3,095, 118in 2017 (United Nations, 2019). FCT, Abuja consists of six Area Councils which includes Abaji, Abuja Municipal, Gwagwalada, Kuje, and Kwali. Multi stage sampling techniques was used for this study. The first involved random selection of four (4) wards. The last stage involved proportional selection of 10% of respondents from the sampling frame. Primary data was used for this study. Data collection was carried out by researchers assisted and by well-trained enumerators using structured questionnaire complemented with interview schedules. Objective I and IV were achieved using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage and mean).

Sampling population of the respondents

State	LGA	Wards	Sampling Frame	Sample Size (10%)
FCT	Abaji	Abaji town	354	35
		Agyana	256	26
		Naharati	174	17
		Nuku	221	22
		Total	4	1005

Sources: National Social Investment Office FCT, Abuja (2016)

Analytical techniques

Personal wellbeing index (PWI)

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Objective II (well-being of CCT beneficiaries) was achieved using Personal Well-being Index (PWI). The international well-being group categories personal well-being index adult scale adopted from (Ajibola and Fatoki (2020)). The scale was operationalized by a number continuum in linear scale that range between 1–10, that is $1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9+10=55$ and then divided by 10 to obtain a mean score of 5.5. Any mean scores ≥ 5.5 was considered as satisfied, while mean scores < 5.5 was considered not satisfied. The procedures that determine the well-being of CCT beneficiaries was based on seven (7) items (standard of living, personal health, life achievements, personal relationship, personal safety, community connectedness and future security). Each of the seven (7) domain scores was summed up to form an average score which represent subjected well-being.

Model specification for effects of Conditional Cash Transfer and well-being of beneficiaries

Objective III was achieved using Logit Regression Model. The model is specified below:

$$\text{Well-being} = (a_0 + a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + a_3X_3 + a_4X_4 + a_5X_5 + a_6X_6 + a_7X_7 + a_8X_8 + a_9X_9 + a_{10}X_{10} + U)$$

Well being CCT (Satisfied= 1; Not satisfied= 0)

X_1 = Age of the participant (years)

X_2 = Level of education of participant (Non-formal = 1; Informal = 2; Formal =)

X_3 = Distance to CCT centre (Km)

X_4 = Income level and savings of the participant SIP (₦)

X_5 = Place of resident (Village =1; Town = 0)

X_6 = membership of cooperative society (number)

X_7 = Health care activities (number)

X_8 = Environmental sanitation = (number)

X_9 = Education/school enrolment (number)

X_{10} = Well-being status score (Satisfied = 1; Not satisfied = 0)

U= random disturbance or error term

Constraints associated with CCT beneficiaries

This was using measured using 3-points Likert scale, and was allotted as follows: very severe 3, severe 2, not severe 1. A mean score of 2.0 was obtained by adding $1+2+3$ and dividing by 3. The decision rule was any mean scores > 2.0 , indicates severe, while scores < 3.0 is termed not severe.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of CCT Beneficiaries

Table 1 revealed that 79.0% of the respondents in the study area were female while 21.0% were male. Larger proportion of women beneficiaries could be due to the fact that the programme is targeted at poor and the vulnerable with the motive of enhancing their wellbeing status. This finding is in consonance with Ude and Brown (2018) who reported that CCT targets more women than men in Cross River State of Nigeria. Table 1 indicated that the mean age of respondents in the study area was 47.3 years. This implies that respondents are in their active and productive age in which respondents would tend to engage in different enterprises in order to boost their wellbeing status. This finding agreed with Nuhu *et al* (2015) who reported that younger women benefitted more in Government empowerment programme in Borno State of Nigeria. Table 1 showed that the most 64.0% of the respondents were married. This finding revealed that most of the respondents were married. This could imply family responsibilities that tend to increase participation in CCT for improved wellbeing status. This finding is in line with Nuhu *et al*. (2015) who reported that larger percentage of women in Borno State of Nigeria were married. The result in Table 1 showed that the mean household size of respondents in Niger State was FCT was 6.0 persons. This implies large family size. Large household could have negative effect on the household size and wellbeing status due to pressure on the available resources within the household. This result is in line with Orbeta (2016) who reported that large household sizes reduce family saving and wellbeing status.

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Results in Table 1 revealed the mean farming experience of farmers in FCT was 16.8 years. This suggests that farmers in the study area had long experience in farming and this could increase level of participation in Conditional Cash Transfer in order to improve their wellbeing status. This finding concurs with that of Baba-Ari *et al.* (2018) who confirmed many years of experience among CCT beneficiaries in North Central of Nigeria. Table 1 showed that the mean years spent in formal education in FCT was 2.5 years. This signifies a low literacy level. However, low literacy level is expected to affect beneficiaries' level of participation and wellbeing status due to inability to perceived new and productive ideas that would enhance their knowledge horizon of CCT beneficiaries in the study area. Table 1 revealed that the mean farm size of farmers in FCT was 2.5 hectares. The finding showed that CCT beneficiaries in the study area operate on a small scale, producing mainly for family consumption. However, farming on a smaller scale could have negative effect on the wellbeing status of CCT beneficiaries in the study area. This finding concurs with that of Adeaga *et al.* (2017) who reported that most of the households in who benefited in the uplifting programme in Nigeria are small scale farmers. Figure in Table 1 indicated that the mean annual income of CCT beneficiaries in FCT was ₦119,901.00, implying that CCT beneficiaries in the study area had low annual income. This is in congruent with the finding of Ayoade and Adeola (2012) who indicated low-income earnings among rural households in Oyo State.

Table: Distribution of respondents according to socioeconomic characteristic (n=100)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex			
Male	21	21.0	
Female	79	79.0	
Age			
<30	12	12.0	47.3
31-40	26	26.0	
41-50	19	19.0	
51-60	28	28.0	
>60	15	15.0	
Marital status			
Single	1	1.0	
Separated	5	5.0	
Married	64	64.0	
Widow	26	26.0	
Divorced	4	4.0	
Household size			
1-5	54	54.0	6.0
6-10	40	40.0	
11-15	6	6.0	
Farming experience			
1-10	36	36.0	16.8
11-20	43	43.0	
21-30	10	10.0	
>30	11	11.0	
Year spent in formal education			
1-6	21	21.0	3.9
7-12	13	13.0	
>12	8	8.0	

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None	58	58.0	
Size of farm land			
<2	64	64.0	2.5
2.1-4	27	27.0	
>4	9	9.0	
Annual income			
<50000	33	33.0	119910
51000-100000	30	30.0	
101000-150000	21	21.0	
151000-200000	5	5.0	
>200000	11	11.0	
Distance to CCT center			
<5	63	63.0	
5.1-10	12	12.0	
>10	25	25.0	

Sources: Field survey, 2023

Wellbeing status of CCT beneficiaries

Table 2 indicated that CCT beneficiaries in were satisfied with the following; personal relationship (\bar{X} =5.64), personal safety (\bar{X} =5.62) and life achievement (\bar{X} =5.62) ranked 1st and 2nd respectively. This signifies that interpersonal relationship that coexists among the beneficiaries in the study area. Also, personal safety indicates high degree of safety and prevention from conflict related issues. This finding is in agreement with that of Ajibola and Fatoki (2020) who reported high level who reported that rice farmers were satisfy with their personal relation and safety in Nasarawa State. However, respondents were not satisfy with community connectedness (\bar{X} =5.47), future security (\bar{X} =5.45), standard of living (\bar{X} =4.90) and personal health (\bar{X} =4.90). The not satisfy responses by the CCT beneficiaries could imply low and unattractive wellbeing status among the rural populace in the study area.

Table 2: Wellbeing status of CCT beneficiaries

Variables	Mean	Ranking	Decision
Standard of living	4.90	7 th	Not satisfy
Personal health	5.26	6 th	Not satisfy
Life achievement	5.62	2 nd	Satisfied
Personal relationship	5.64	1 st	Satisfied
Personal safety	5.62	2 nd	Satisfied
Community connectedness	5.47	4 th	Not satisfy
Future security	5.45	5 th	Not satisfy

Sources: Field survey, 2023

Effects of CCT on the well-being status of beneficiaries

Table 3 revealed the result of Logit Regression was used to determine effects of CCT on the well-being of beneficiaries. The results showed Pseudo R² of 0.5102, signifying that about 51.0% of variation wellbeing status was explained by the independent variables included in the model, The chi-square statistics 59.51 was significant at 1% level of probability indicating fitness of the model. From the Z values, five out of the nine variables included in the model were statically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% in the result. The coefficient of educational level (0.3214183) was positively significant at 1% level of probability, indicating that increase in formal education will increase CCT beneficiaries' wellbeing status. The coefficient of distance to CCT center (0.2295646) was negatively significant at 10% level of probability, implying that less distance to CCT center

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will increase the wellbeing status of the beneficiaries. The coefficient of cooperative (1.36954) was positively significant at 5% level of probability. This shows that membership of cooperative will avail beneficiaries' access to input, incentives and capital that tend to increase their wellbeing status. The coefficient access to sanitation (0.9016355) was positively significant at 10% level of probability, indicating that access to sanitation is an evidence of improved wellbeing status. The coefficient of enrolment of children in school (1.054859) was positively at 5% level of probability, indicating that increment in number of children that enroll is an indication of improved wellbeing status.

Table 3: Effects of CCT on the Well-Being of Beneficiaries (n=100)

Variables	Coefficient	Z-value
Age	0.0174115	0.47
Educational level	0.3214183	2.57***
Distance to CCT center	-0.2295646	-1.78*
Annual income	-1.63e-06	-0.39
Training	-1.253806	-0.98
Cooperative	1.36954	1.95**
Access to healthcare	0.1277014	0.36
Access to sanitation	0.9016355	1.88*
Enrolment of children in school	1.054859	2.06**
Wellbeing score	-.0240057	-0.97
Constant	-.5837372	-0.24
Pseudo R ²	0.5102	
Chi ²	59.51***	
Log likelihood	-28.570914	

Source: Field survey, 2023

*** Significant at 1% level of probability, **=Significant at 5% level of probability, ,

*=Significant at 10% level of probability

Constraints associated with CCT beneficiaries

Table 4 showed corruption among official (\bar{X} =2.50) ranked 1st as the most severe associated with CCT. This arises from the action of corrupt officials that divert fund and input wrong and inaccessible beneficiaries. Poor road network (\bar{X} =2.32) ranked 2nd, this implies lack of pliable roads to the communities where the beneficiaries scatter. Lack of trust among beneficiaries (\bar{X} =2.24) ranked 3rd, indicating lack of confidence on the officials and among the beneficiaries themselves. Other constraints associated with CCT include poor statistical data (\bar{X} =2.19), inadequate funding (\bar{X} =2.12), poor government policy (\bar{X} =2.10). This finding agreed with that of Ibrahim (2017) who reported that poor funding and corruption among officials were the major problem facing social investment programme in Nigeria. The result is also consistent with the findings of Alalade *et al.* (2020) who opined that bad attitude from government poverty eradication programmes fail in Nigeria. In similar vein, Ike and Uzokwe (2012) asserted nonchalant attitude of government officers, inconsistency in government policies and untimely release of funds were the major constraints militating against participation in government developmental programmes in Nigeria. Furthermore, Akujuru and Enyioko (2019) also reported corruption among officials and poor road network are big blows to participation in social investment programmes in Nigeria.

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Table 4: Constraints associated with CCT beneficiaries (n=100)

Variables	Very severe	Severe	Not severe	Sum	Mean	Ranking	Decision
Corrupt among officials	58 (58.0)	34 (34.0)	8 (8.0)	250	2.50	1 st	Severe
Inadequate monitoring and evaluation	16 (16.0)	76 (76.0)	8 (8.0)	208	2.08	7 th	Severe
Lack of trust among beneficiaries	36 (36.0)	52 (52.0)	12 (12.0)	224	2.24	3 rd	Severe
Lack of continuity	21 (21.0)	64 (64.0)	15 (15.0)	206	2.06	8 th	Severe
Multiple and wrong beneficiaries	10 (10.0)	60 (60.0)	30 (30.0)	180	1.80	9 th	Not severe
Poor statistical data	33 (33.0)	53 (53.0)	14 (14.0)	219	2.19	4 th	Severe
Poor road network	42 (42.0)	48 (48.0)	10 (24.0)	232	2.32	2 nd	Severe
Poor government policy	34 (34.0)	42 (42.0)	24 (24.0)	210	2.10	6 th	Severe
Inadequate funding	38 (38.0)	36 (36.0)	26 (26.0)	212	2.12	5 th	Severe

Sources: Field survey, 2023

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on this finding it can be concluded that majority of the beneficiaries were female in their active age with low literacy level. CCT beneficiaries were satisfied with their personal relationship, life achievement and personal safety. The coefficient of educational level, distance to CCT center, cooperative, access to sanitation and enrolment of children in school had effect on the wellbeing status of CCT beneficiaries. The most constraints associated with CCT were corrupt among officials, poor road network and lack of trust among beneficiaries. It is recommended that government should inject more funds to the programme in order to enhance beneficiaries' wellbeing status, intervention programme should be brought closer to beneficiaries dwelling place for easy accessibility. Lastly, it is recommended that beneficiaries should diversify into other income generating activities for better standard of living.

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